

Electrical Asymmetric-Flow Field-Flow Fractionation with a multi-detector array platform for the characterization of metallic nanoparticles with different coatings

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Abstract

Electrical Asymmetric-Flow Field-Flow Fractionation (EAF4) is a new and interesting analytical technique recently proposed for the characterization of metallic nanoparticles (NPs). It has the potential to simultaneously provide relevant information about size and electrical parameters, such as electrophoretic mobility (μ) and zeta potential (ζ), of individual NP populations in an online instrumental setup with an array of detectors. However, several chemical and instrumental conditions involved in this technique are definitely influential, and only few applications have been proposed until now. In the present work, an EAF4 system has been used with different detectors, ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis), multi-angle light scattering (MALS), and inductively coupled plasma with triple quadrupole mass spectrometry (ICP-TQ-MS) for the characterization of gold, silver, and platinum NPs with both citrate and phosphate coatings. The behavior of NPs has been studied in terms of retention time and signal intensity under both positive and negative current with results depending on the coating. Carrier composition, particularly ionic strength, was found to be critical to achieve satisfactory recoveries and a reliable measurement of electrical parameters. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) has been used as a comparative technique for these parameters. The NovaChem surfactant mix (0.01 %) showed a quantitative recovery (93 ± 1 %) of the membrane, but the carrier had to be modified by increasing the ionic strength with $200\ \mu\text{M}$ of Na_2CO_3 to achieve consistent μ values. However, ζ was one order of magnitude lower in EAF4-UV-vis-MALS than in DLS, probably due to different electric processes in the channel. From a practical point of view, EAF4 technique is still in its infancy and further studies are necessary for a robust implementation in the characterization of NPs.

Keywords: electrical asymmetric-flow field-flow fractionation; inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry; dynamic light scattering; metallic nanoparticles.

1. Introduction

In recent years, metallic nanoparticles (NPs) have been extensively studied due to their unique properties and their numerous applications in many fields. This massive use requires appropriate analytical methodologies to satisfy the quality control of the synthesized/produced NPs in industrial/commercial production and to detect and quantify NPs in samples of social interest [1]. Analytical chemistry of NPs includes not only the traditional quantitative determination, but also the measurement of physical parameters, such as size (size distribution), shape, agglomeration, or surface charge, which provide relevant information about the behavior of NPs. The inherent charge of NPs has effects in aggregation/agglomeration, that is, charge might be behind changes in size and/or size distribution, so information about electrical properties is relevant as well. Nowadays, it is accepted that a wide range of techniques, namely microscopy, spectroscopy, light-scattering and others, are necessary to get a full characterization of NPs [2].

Instrumental separation techniques are increasingly incorporated to measure NPs because they provide information about size and concentration at the same time [3–5]. Among them, Asymmetric-Flow Field-Flow Fractionation (AF4) has proved to be suitable for the size fractionation of NPs [1, 6]. This technique is easy to couple to a number of detectors, such as ultraviolet/visible absorption (UV-vis), multi-angle light scattering (MALS), fluorescence, and refractive index, which give different but complementary information. An interesting approach is to set up an array of all these non-destructive detectors after AF4. Moreover, the coupling to inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) enables the quantification of NPs at ppt levels with specific, multi-elemental, and multi-isotopic detection [7–10].

As for electrical parameters, Electrical Field-Flow Fractionation with oscillating or cyclical applied fields (Cy/ElFFF) has contributed to separate charged analytes in a specifically built-in channel, which consists of two frits on the top and bottom that act as electrodes [11]. These electrodes can be made up of graphite, platinized stainless steel or titanium. The simplest theoretical approach indicates that the velocity of a charged species in an electric field is proportional to the applied voltage (E) and the proportionality constant is electrophoretic mobility (μ). This is a key parameter to determine because it accounts

for the behavior of the charged species in a particular medium and separations of NPs by Cy/EIFFF have been achieved on the basis of their size and μ , indeed [12–14]. However, the instrumental setup for fractionation was custom made, without the possibility of measuring μ other than in a separate off-line instrument. This drawback can be circumvented by recent instrumental developments, which have given way to Electrical Asymmetric-Flow Field-Flow Fractionation (EAF4) [15]. This emerging technique is a promising alternative to characterize NPs for size and electrical properties simultaneously. In EAF4, an electrical field is applied in addition to the regular cross-flow, both perpendicularly to the direction of separation across the flow channel, so fractionation is influenced by diffusion and surface charge (Figure 1). The final location of the NPs in the channel wall determines the relative retention of the particles. This way, specific conductivity (k_c) turns E into effective field (E_{eff}) and velocity of NPs into drift velocity (v_{EP}), being μ calculated as the quotient of v_{EP} over E_{eff} . Another key parameter that can be derived from μ is zeta-potential (ζ), which is related to the intermolecular electrostatic interactions between species in solution/dispersion. These two parameters estimate the physical stability of the suspension and the possible interactions of NPs, and they both can be derived from the fractograms by the data treatment software of the EAF4 instrument through the Smoluchowski equation without the need of further external equipment [16].

Electrical Asymmetric-Flow Field-Flow Fractionation requires the fine selection of a lot of factors that influence the location of the analytes in the channel and, consequently, the fractionation. Thus, a careful selection of the carrier composition as well as diffusion (tip, focus, cross flows) and electrical (applied field, conductivity) parameters is critical. EAF4 is still in its infancy and the scarce studies carried out so far to optimize the carrier for the determination of μ and/or ζ are limited to exosomes, liposomes, proteins, and polystyrene latex particles [15, 17, 18]. Other authors have used EAF4 for Au nanorods recently, but only to confirm that those NPs carry negative charge and thereby confirming the ζ obtained by a separate instrument [19].

The aim of this work is to conduct a survey on the possibilities of EAF4 for the characterization of spherical metallic NPs of gold, silver, and platinum (AuNPs, AgNPs, and PtNPs) with both citrate and phosphate coatings in different carriers using a multi-

detector array platform that simultaneously provides relevant and complementary information on size and electrical properties in a short time. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) has been used as a classical technique for comparison.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Reagents

All chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade. Solutions were prepared in ultrapure water (18.2 M Ω cm) obtained from a Milli-Q[®] A10TM water purification system (Millipore Corporation, USA). Commercial solutions of 30 nm spherical PtNPs, AuNPs, and AgNPs stabilized in 2 mM citrate were purchased from nanoComposix (USA). Also, a commercial solution of 30 nm spherical AuNP stabilized in 0.1 mM phosphate buffered saline (PBS) was acquired from Aldrich Chemical Company (Milwaukee, USA).

Thallium (1,000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Tl in 5% HNO₃) and platinum (1,000 \pm 3 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Pt in 5% HCl) solutions were acquired from Inorganic Ventures (USA). A gold standard solution (1,025 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Au³⁺ in 5% HCl) was purchased from Aldrich Chemical Company (Milwaukee, USA). HCl (37%), and NaH₂PO₄·H₂O were purchased from Scharlab (Spain). HNO₃ (69%), Na₂HPO₄·12H₂O, and Na₂CO₃, were obtained from Merck (Germany). Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and NovaChem surfactant 100 were acquired from Acros Organics (Spain) and from Postnova Analytics (Germany), respectively.

2.2. Apparatus and instrumental features

The EAF4 system was an AF2000 (Postnova Analytics, Germany) equipped with an electrical analytical fractionation channel, which is connected to the top and bottom titanium electrodes. The applied electrical field was controlled by an electrical FFF module (PN2410, Postnova Analytics, Germany). This module is equipped with a built-in conductivimeter. The measured conductivity enables the calculation of μ and ζ . A membrane of regenerated cellulose with a molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) of 10 kDa was used as the accumulation wall. The trapezoidal channel was 27.7 cm long and from 2 to 0.5 cm wide, and the spacer was 350 μm thick. The flow rate was 0.5 mL min⁻¹. The EAF4 system was coupled to a UV-vis detector (PN3212, Postnova Analytics, Germany)

and a 9 angle MALS detector (PN3609, Postnova Analytics, Germany). The 9 scattering angles were normalized with respect to the 90° angle measuring a 60 nm Latex standard (0.05 mg mL⁻¹) fractionated by EAF4. The instrument control and data analysis of the EAF4 system, as well as the data evaluation of the UV-vis and MALS detectors, were performed by the NovaFFF AF2000 Control software (Postnova Analytics, Germany). The carrier solution was filtered through 0.1 µm Teflon membrane filters (Postnova Analytics, Germany) and degassed before using. The different metallic NPs in carrier solution were filtered through 0.2 µm filters (Agilent Technologies, Econofilter Nylon diameter 13 mm) before injection into EAF4 system. This step avoids clogging of some EAF4 components and ensures a homogeneous diffusion mode without loss of NPs [6].

An inductively coupled plasma-triple quadrupole-mass spectrometry (ICP-TQ-MS) system (iCAP TQ, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany), equipped with a Micro Mist nebulizer and a cyclonic spray chamber, was employed as a detector by direct coupling to EAF4. The equipment was tuned daily for the highest sensitivity in the single quadrupole kinetic energy discrimination mode (SQ-KED) with He as collision gas. The raw data of the NP transient isotope signal and Thallium (15 µg L⁻¹, internal standard used to correct signal drift) were further processed using the Qtegra™ Intelligent Scientific Data Solution™ (ISDS) software. The detailed measurement conditions of EAF4 and all detectors are summarized in Table 1.

A Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Panalytical, UK) was used to obtain the zeta-average size and ζ of the NPs. The DLS measurements were carried out using a dust-free disposable cuvette (DTS0012, Malvern Analytical, UK). The volume was 1 mL, the backscatter angle was 173°, and the temperature 25°C. Three consecutive measurements were performed using a minimum of 11 runs. The zeta-average size was determined by averaging three replicate values. For the determination of ζ , 700 µL of each sample were transferred to a disposable zeta cell (DTS1070, Malvern Panalytical, UK). After 2 min of equilibration to a temperature of 25°C, three consecutive measurements were performed. The Smoluchowski approximation was used for the calculation of ζ [16]. The mean value was obtained from three replicates.

An advanced ZX3 Vortex (Velp Scientifica, Italy) was employed to avoid the aggregation/agglomeration of NPs.

2.3. Preparation and characterization of the NP solutions.

The different metallic NPs were homogenized with vortex agitation at 1,200 rpm for 1 min before using. These nano-sized particles were diluted in the carrier (1:500 for EAF4-ICP-TQ-MS and 1:10 or 1:5 for EAF4-UV-vis-MALS), vortexed for 10 s and filtered through 0.2 μm nylon filters before injection.

Their concentrations were quantified (60 ± 2 , 56 ± 5 , 26 ± 1 for $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for PtNP, AuNP, and AgNP-citrate, respectively, and 58 ± 3 for AuNP-PBS, $n = 3$) by ICP-MS after microwave digestion as previously described [6]. The zeta-average sizes measured by DLS were 38.9 ± 0.8 nm, 49.8 ± 0.6 nm, 44.7 ± 0.6 nm for citrate capped PtNPs, AuNPs and AgNPs, respectively, and 39.2 ± 0.5 nm for AuNP-PBS. The TEM analysis provided by the manufacturer verified monodispersed NPs with a nominal diameter of 31 ± 3 nm, 30 ± 3 nm, 29 ± 3 nm for PtNPs, AuNPs, AgNPs stabilized in citrate, respectively, and $31 - 43$ nm for AuNP-PBS.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Optimization of the carrier composition

The EAF4 technique is a combination of an electric field and asymmetric-flow in the field-flow fractionation. The fractionation method used was modified from a technical application note [20] (Table 1). One of the critical variables that could affect the fractionation of NPs by EAF4 is the carrier composition. A correct selection reduces the loss of particulate material by electrostatic attraction between the NPs and the membrane. For this purpose, sodium carbonate (25 μM , pH = 7.3), SDS (0.01 %, pH = 6.0), PBS-SDS (1 mM PBS + 0.01 % SDS at pH = 7.0), and NovaChem (mix of non-ionic and ionic detergents) (0.01 %, pH = 8.2) were investigated according to previous studies in the literature for metallic NPs [1, 6, 14, 21–25]. The pH of the carriers was adequate to keep the negative charge of the citrate coating and thus avoid aggregation/agglomeration. For this study, 50 μL of the 30 nm PtNPs diluted in the different tested carrier solutions were injected into the EAF4-ICP-TQ-MS.

Recovery rate (%) was calculated to assess the capacity to fractionate analytes without a significant loss of material, according to previous studies [6, 25, 26]. Thus, the sample is injected successively with and without the application of a cross-flow field, the peak area is integrated in each case, and the difference represents the analyte loss in the system. According to the equations suggested in literature [24], the membrane recoveries using the different carrier composition were calculated (Table 2). The use of sodium carbonate at a concentration of 25 μM represents the worst carrier liquid to fractionate the PtNPs in terms of recovery rate ($57 \pm 1 \%$). In addition, it is of special relevance to indicate that the separation was not possible for this PtNP size and void peak (data not shown). In the case of SDS (0.01 %), the recovery rate was significantly higher and quantitative ($90.1 \pm 0.5 \%$) and the fractionation profile revealed a clearly defined peak with a retention time of 16 min. Also, the separation between void and 30 nm PtNP peaks was achieved (data not shown). The addition of PBS at a concentration of 1 mM to SDS (0.01 %) was tested as carrier based on previous studies [6], but the performance did not improve and even decreased ($87 \pm 2 \%$). Finally, with the NovaChem surfactant mix (0.01 %), an adequate separation between the void peak and the 30 nm PtNP peak, with retention times of 7.7 and 11 min, respectively, was achieved (data not shown). Moreover, its recovery rate was slightly more satisfactory ($93 \pm 1 \%$). Therefore, this was selected as the most adequate carrier liquid for the study of 30 nm PtNPs via EAF4-ICP-TQ-MS. This recovery rate is in the range obtained in literature for this carrier in the separation of 100 nm TiO_2NPs [23] and higher than that obtained for 21 nm iron oxide NPs [22]. Another application of NovaChem for TiO_2NPs was recently published, but recovery range was not calculated [21].

3.2. Influence of the electric field

In order to explore the possibilities of the application of the additional electric field to the fractionation, citrate coated 30 nm PtNPs (dilution 1:500 in NovaChem 0.01 %) were injected at different current intensities (0, ± 0.1 , and ± 0.2 mA) while keeping the other fractionation parameters constant (Table 1). It should be pointed out that the citrate coating gives a negative surface charge to the PtNPs. The electric field induces a net surface charge on the accumulation wall, which changes the elution time of the charged NP as a function of the direction and strength of the electric force applied to the NPs.

Figure 2 illustrates the fractograms of 30 nm PtNPs obtained by EAF4 at different electrical currents with the optimized carrier and the instrumental conditions summarized in Table 1. The results showed that when an electric field was applied, electric field-dependent shifts in the retention time and changes in the relative signal of NPs-peak occurred. When a negative electric current was applied (the bottom and top electrodes are the anode (+) and cathode (-), respectively), the fractionation time of PtNP increased from approximately 11 min to 13.4 or 13.8 min for -0.1 or -0.2 mA, respectively. This could be because the negatively charged citrate coated PtNPs are attracted to the membrane surface, which is placed on the bottom electrode, that is, the anode. This keeps PtNPs in the area of the channel with a low velocity profile as shown in Figure 1. An increase in the relative signal intensity was observed with the greatest current applied, -0.2 mA. This can be due to a more intense attraction of the PtNPs to the bottom electrode and, consequently, to an additional pseudo-focusing on the membrane. Additionally, the separation of the void peak is improved. Conversely, with the positive electrical current, the retention time of PtNPs decreased from 11 min to 9.4 and 9.3 min for +0.1 and +0.2 mA, respectively. This can be due to an electrostatic repulsion between the membrane surface and the analyte, which facilitates the placing of PtNPs in the part of the channel with a higher velocity profile. An increased peak intensity (0.05 to 0.08 or 0.10, approximately) was observed, which can also be explained by sample repulsion from the bottom electrode (cathode) to the negatively charged PtNPs. Both repulsion and diffusion operate in the same way, so they take the PtNPs towards the channel flow.

The behavior of the 30 nm citrate coated AuNPs and AgNPs, and PBS coated AuNPs was studied with the same range of electrical currents. Figure 3A shows the fractograms of 30 nm citrate coated AuNPs. A decrease in retention times for positive currents and an increase with negative currents was observed together with a signal increase, just like citrate coated PtNPs. Similar results were obtained for 30 nm AgNPs (Figure S1). In the case of PBS coated AuNPs, the same trend for electric field-dependent shifts in the fractionation time was observed (Figure 3B). However, the changes in relative signal intensity follow an opposite pattern. It must be noted that the coating of AuNPs is different, PBS. At the pH of the carrier, 8.2, there are two negative charges in the

phosphate groups ($pK_{a3} = 12.2$) whereas there are three negative charges in the citrate groups ($pK_{a3} = 6.4$). This difference could be behind the different behavior. As opposed to what happened for citrate coated AuNPs, the relative intensity of PBS-AuNPs decreased as the positive electric current increased. A possible reason is that the more positive current, the more attraction to the upper electrode (anode), and the fewer AuNPs under the influence of the carrier flow. As for negative currents, the signal intensity was the same as without electrical field for -0.1 mA and decreased for -0.2 mA. This indicates a stronger electrostatic attraction of the PBS-AuNPs towards the bottom channel (cathode) as the negative current increases. This interaction would prevent a fraction of PBS-AuNPs from being released to the channel flow. Therefore, the coating and carrier composition are critical factors that should be carefully considered as they determine the behavior of NPs in electrical fields in terms of both fractionation and signal intensity.

3.3. Estimation of electrical parameters

The electrical parameters, μ and ζ , were estimated for citrate coated PtNPs by EAF4 coupled to the array detector system of MALS and UV-vis, and also by the DLS Zetasizer instrument. The results are summarized in Table 3.

The μ obtained with either EAF4-MALS or EAF4-UV-vis detection was calculated as the slope of the E_{eff} vs. v_{EP} plot. Therefore, the determination coefficient R^2 was taken as the degree of the reliability in the estimation of μ . The SDS (0.01 %) carrier showed R^2 below 0.45, whereas NovaChem (0.01 %) pH=8.2, the carrier previously selected as optimum for the fractionation of these PtNPs using ICP-MS detection, showed pretty higher R^2 coefficients, yet still below 0.85. Another carrier tested was Na_2CO_3 at concentrations of 25, 100, and 400 μM . In all these cases, the obtained R^2 were below 0.65. These poor values can explain the differences in the measurement of μ by EAF4-MALS and EAF4-UV-vis in relation to DLS. However, an increase in conductivity by adding 200 μM Na_2CO_3 to the NovaChem carrier resulted in an increase in R^2 and, consequently, the obtained values of μ with MALS or UV-vis after EAF4, were closer to DLS.

In the estimation of ζ , the charge at the surface and the characteristics of the surrounding solution should be considered. For example, it is known that ζ strongly

depends on ionic strength, as it is closely related to the Debye-Hückel length, and on pH, too [17]. The values of ζ by EAF4-MALS or EAF4-UV-vis were different from those by DLS, even though they were closer in the case of the addition of 200 μM Na_2CO_3 to the carrier (one order of magnitude different). Moreover, it was also observed that ζ decreases strongly with increasing ionic strength in all cases, which is consistent with previous studies [14, 17]. In the presence of a more saline solution, the values found for EAF4-MALS and EAF4-UV-vis became closer to each other. The gap can be because measurements by MALS and UV-vis are carried out after an AF4 separation, so it is only a single size NP that is measured. In contrast, in DLS it is the bulk solution that is measured, which includes all NP sizes. Other possible reasons are interactions of NPs that may occur in the channel whilst migration takes place, electrolysis by-products or components from non-Faradaic processes (e.g., ions adsorbed or accumulated on electrodes), which, in turn, can change the solution pH [27]. This just cannot happen in a static DLS measuring cell and could justify the different values obtained, but further research is necessary to clarify this point.

4. Conclusions

EAF4 is a promising tool to get information on the electrical properties of NPs, but the studies are scarce at present. In the present work, the behavior of citrate coated PtNPs, AuNPs and AgNPs as well as PBS coated AuNPs was investigated. The carrier composition was found to be a critical parameter to achieve adequate recoveries and reliable estimations of electrical parameters. The influence of the current applied on the fractionation times was independent from the nature or the coating of the NPs. However, the current intensity seemed to depend on the NP coating, even with opposite trends from one coating to another.

The EAF4-UV-vis-MALS approach allows to determine the electrical properties based on electrophoretic mobility, such as ζ and the effective net charge of the PtNPs, but there

are limitations due to the carrier composition, particularly to the ionic strength. The different values found by EAF4-UV-vis-MALS and DLS can be attributed to the intrinsic differences in the measuring itself, with DLS being a static technique and AF4 a dynamic one. Plus, in DLS it is the bulk that is measured whereas EAF4 allows a size fractionation before measuring. Therefore, the present approach shows the advantage that it can measure these parameters in polydisperse samples.

This technique is still in its infancy, so more research is necessary to make the most of it in several ways. Thus, further studies should be carried out, especially in the field of NPs because of the increasing social demand of information about these new materials.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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